

The Algebra of the Equality on Complex Numbers IV

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Abstract

On this work its addressed some algebraic properties about the quirality of complex plane using the function Q . Besides its gives a definition of scalar product in terms of Add_{map} , $Prod_{map}$ and Q functions; some property of groups for the Argand product and equality by translation $=_T$ named "the group of translations" and the field of real number and its relation with $Im(Add_{map})$ and $Im(Prod_{map})$

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Notation.

All \cdot ("dot symbol") symbols represent and Argand's Product when is operated between two 2-tuples; in other case are multiplications between scalars.

1 Quiral Properties about the Complex Plane

Figure 1: Quirality on Cartesian Plane on \mathbb{R}^2

Lets define the function

$Q := Quirality$ like

$Q : X \times X \rightarrow X \times X'$

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where

$$(a, b) \in X \times X \text{ and } (a, -b) \in X \times X'$$

such that

$$Q(a, b) = (a, -b)$$

on Argand's Product we have

$$Q[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = Q(ac - bd, ad + bc) = (ac - bd, -ad - bc)$$

while if we take

$$Q(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d) = (a, -b) \cdot (c, -d) = (ac - bd, -ad - bc)$$

Hence

$$Q[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = Q(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d)$$

Implying that Q function is an homomorphism.

Properties about Q function

1) Q injective

Lets take

$$Q(a, b) = Q(c, d)$$

hence

$$(a, -b) = (c, -d)$$

this imply that necessarily

$$a = c \text{ and } b = d$$

hence Q is injective

2) Q surjective

With

$$Q(a, b) = (a, -b) \in \mathfrak{R}^2$$

hence Q is surjective

Therefore Q is bijective

Q function and Add_{map} function

*) **$Add_{map}(Q(a,b) \cdot (c,d))$ is an homomorphism**

Lets apply Add_{map} function to early results

$$Add_{map}\{Q[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)]\} = Add_{map}[Q(ac - bd, ad + bc)]$$

$$= Add_{map}(ac - bd, -ad - bc)$$

$$= ac - bd - ad - bc$$

with $-bd < bd$ we have (ref[2])

$$ac - bd - ad - bc < ac + bd - ad - bc$$

$$= ac + bd - ad - bc$$

$$= (a - b) \cdot (c - d)$$

$$= Add_{map}(a, -b) \cdot Add_{map}(c, -d)$$

$$= Add_{map}[Q(a, b)] \cdot Add_{map}[Q(c, d)]$$

Hence

$$Add_{map}\{Q[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)]\} =_A Add_{map}[Q(a, b)] \cdot Add_{map}[Q(c, d)]$$

fulfills

If we substitute $Q(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = Q(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d)$ on left side of the equation we have

$$Add_{map}\{Q[(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d)]\} = Add_{map}[(a, -b) \cdot (c, -d)]$$

$$= Add_{map}(ac - bd, -ad - bc)$$

$$= ac - bd - ad - bc$$

$$< ac + bd - ad - bc$$

and so on ... until obtain the equality

$$=_A Add_{map}[Q(a, b)] \cdot Add_{map}[Q(c, d)]$$

Therefore Add_{map} homomorphism applied to Q function over Argand's product is an homomorphism of the form

$$f(x \cdot y) = f(x) \cdot f(y)$$

Q function and Prod_{map} function

***) Prod_{map}(Q(a,b)·(c,d))** is an homomorphism

Lets now prove same property for Prod_{map} function

$$Prod_{map}\{Q[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)]\} = Prod_{map}[Q(ac - bd, ad + bc)]$$

$$= Prod_{map}(ac - bd, -ad - bc)$$

$$= (ac - bd) \cdot (-ad - bc)$$

$$= -a^2cd - abc^2 + abd^2 + b^2cd$$

with $a = b$

$$= -a^2cd - a^2c^2 + a^2d^2 + a^2cd$$

$$= -a^2c^2 + a^2d^2$$

$$= a^2(d^2 - c^2)$$

with $c = d$

$$0 < a^2 \cdot c \cdot d = a^2cd$$

$$= Prod(a, -b) \cdot Prod(c, -d)$$

$$= Prod[Q(a, b)] \cdot Prod[Q(c, d)]$$

Hence

$$Prod_{map}\{Q[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)]\} =_A Prod[(Q(a, b)] \cdot Prod[Q(c, d)]$$

If we substitute $Q(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = Q(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d)$ on left side of the equation we have

$$Prod_{map}\{Q(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d)\} = Prod_{map}[(a, -b) \cdot (c, -d)]$$

$$= Prod_{map}(ac - bd, -ad - bc)$$

$$= -a^2cd - abc^2 + abd^2 + b^2cd$$

with $a = b$

$$= -a^2cd - a^2c^2 + a^2d^2 + a^2cd$$

$$= a^2(d^2 - c^2)$$

with $d = c$

$$0 < a^2cd$$

and so on... hence

$$Prod_{map}\{Q(a, b) \cdot Q(c, d)\} =_A Prod[Q(a, b)] \cdot Prod[Q(c, d)]$$

Therefore $Prod_{map}$ homomorphism applied to Q function over Argand's product is an homomorphism of the form

$$f(x \cdot y) = f(x) \cdot f(y)$$

Scalar Product and Monoid Homomorphism

On ref[3] scalar product was define like

With $\vec{a} = (a_1, a_2)$ and $\vec{b} = (b_1, b_2)$ we have

$$|\vec{a}| = \sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2}$$

$$|\vec{b}| = \sqrt{b_1^2 + b_2^2}$$

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2}) \cdot (\sqrt{b_1^2 + b_2^2}) \cos(\alpha)$$

In terms of Prod and Add function scalar product can be written as

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{Prod_{map}(a_1, a_1) + Prod_{map}(a_2, a_2)}) \cdot (\sqrt{Prod_{map}(b_1, b_1) + Prod_{map}(b_2, b_2)}) \cos(\alpha)$$

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(a_1, a_1), Prod_{map}(a_2, a_2))}) \cdot (\sqrt{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(b_1, b_1), Prod_{map}(b_2, b_2))}) \cos(\alpha)$$

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(a_1, a_1), Prod_{map}(a_2, a_2))}) \cdot (\sqrt{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(b_1, b_1), Prod_{map}(b_2, b_2))}) \cos(\alpha)$$

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(a_1, a_1), Prod_{map}(a_2, a_2))}) \cdot Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(b_1, b_1), Prod_{map}(b_2, b_2)) \cos(\alpha)$$

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(a_1, a_1), \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(a_2, a_2)) \cdot \text{Add}_{\text{map}}(\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(b_1, b_1), \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(b_2, b_2))}) \cos(\alpha)$$

$$(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}) = (\sqrt{\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(a_1, a_1), \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(a_2, a_2)), \text{Add}_{\text{map}}(\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(b_1, b_1), \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(b_2, b_2)))}) \cos(\alpha)$$

The angle of the scalar product can be obtained since the law of cosines:

$$A^2 = B^2 + C^2 - 2BC \cos(\alpha)$$

$$\alpha = \arccos\left\{\frac{A^2 - B^2 - C^2}{-2BC}\right\}$$

In terms of Prod_{map} and Add_{map}

$$\alpha = \arccos\left\{\frac{\text{Prod}(A,A) - \text{Prod}(B,B) - \text{Prod}(C,C)}{-2\text{Prod}(B,C)}\right\}$$

$$\alpha = \arccos\{\text{Prod}(\text{Prod}(A, A) - \text{Prod}(B, B) - \text{Prod}(C, C), -2\text{Prod}(B, C))\}$$

$$\alpha = \arccos\{\text{Prod}(Q(\text{Prod}(A, A) - \text{Prod}(B, B) - \text{Prod}(C, C), 2\text{Prod}(B, C)))\}$$

with

$$* = \text{Prod}(A, A) - \text{Prod}(B, B) - \text{Prod}(C, C)$$

and

$$** = -2\text{Prod}(B, C)$$

$$\alpha = \arccos\{\text{Prod}(Q(*, **))\}$$

Like every term considered like $\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(a, b)$ is positive we can establish next conditions:

$$\text{When } * < 0; \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(Q(*, **)) > 0; 0 \leq \alpha < 90$$

$$\text{When } * = 0; \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(Q(*, **)) = 0; \alpha = 90$$

$$\text{When } * > 0; \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(Q(*, **)) < 0; 90 < \alpha \leq 180$$

By the other hand for B and A we have:

$$B = |\vec{b}| = \sqrt{b_1^2 + b_2^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(\text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(b_1, b_1), \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(b_2, b_2))}$$

$$\text{and same for A; } (A = |\vec{a}| = \sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2})$$

While for C is written as

$$C = \vec{ba} = \sqrt{(b_1 - a_1)^2 + (b_2 - a_2)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(b_1, -a_1))^2 + (\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(b_2, -a_2))^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_1, a_1)))^2 + (\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_2, a_2)))^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{(\text{Prod}(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_1, a_1)), \text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_1, a_1))) + \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_2, a_2)), \text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_2, a_2))))}$$

$$= \sqrt{\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(\text{Prod}(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_1, a_1)), \text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_1, a_1))), \text{Prod}_{\text{map}}(\text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_2, a_2)), \text{Add}_{\text{map}}(Q(b_2, a_2)))}$$

Is important to note that the properties about Prod_{map} function establish a second equality for next term about α :

$$\alpha = \arccos\left\{\frac{\text{Prod}(A,A) - \text{Prod}(B,B) - \text{Prod}(C,C)}{-2\text{Prod}(B,C)}\right\}$$

i.e.

$\alpha' = \arccos\{Prod(Q(**, *))\}$ and same trichotomy conditions given about $*$ to define α

Let define next two sets to establish the meaning of quirality about α

$$R = \{(x, y) \in \mathfrak{R} \mid * \in X \wedge ** \in Y\}$$

$$S = \{(x, y) \in \mathfrak{R} \mid ** \in X \wedge * \in Y\}$$

Applying Q function to both sets we have:

$$Q : R \rightarrow R'$$

$$Q : S \rightarrow S'$$

With the change of sign on second coordinate like was established. Same as for \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{S} we have that

$$R' \neq S$$

Taking into account the trichotomy conditions established for α and α' we have that

$$Prod_{map}[Q(*, **)] = Prod_{map}[Q(**, *)]$$

Naming P like the set that contain the results of both $Prod_{map}$ function on $Q(a, b)$ pairs we have:

$$Prod_{map} : S' \rightarrow P_1$$

$$Prod_{map} : R' \rightarrow P_2$$

By equality condition for $Prod_{map}$ we have:

$$P_1 \cup P_2 = P_1 = P_2$$

also

$$P_1 \cap P_2 = P_1 = P_2$$

by this reason $\arccos(Prod_{map}[Q(a, b)])$ for both sets (\mathbf{R} and \mathbf{S}) give same results.

Lets use the abstract equality to establish next relation

$$-\alpha =_A \alpha ; (\text{i.e } -\alpha < \alpha)$$

And lets apply cosine function from both sides hence

$$\cos(-\alpha) = \cos(\alpha)$$

Now remember that cosine function fulfills the property to be even; i.e.

$$f(-x) = f(x)$$

Note that the geometrical meaning of $-\alpha$ is established through the direction of rotation. On this case $-\alpha$ is clockwise direction. Only through multiply α by (-1) and subsequently use of *abstract equality* we can establish a connection between both Cartesian planes (clockwise and anticlockwise).

Under the application of $Prod_{map}$ function and $\arccos(Prod_{map}(Q(a, b)))$ the next relation between quadrants fulfilled:

$$QuadrantI = Q_{map}(QuadrantIV)$$

$$QuadrantII = Q_{map}(QuadrantIII)$$

Where $Q_{map}(Quadrant K)$ denotes the application of Q_{map} function over all pairs of the quadrant numbering with K. While using the property about the area of squares on Quadrant I and Quadrant II to define $-a =_A a$ we can establish besides that:

$$QuadrantI = QuadrantII$$

i.e.

$$Q_{map}(QuadrantIV) = Q_{map}(QuadrantIII)$$

This means that under the early established algebraic geometric properties we can obtain a Cartesian plane where all quadrants are equivalent under rotation; implying that any sense can be given to the property to be quiral and only the magnitude of a rotation define by two vector with center on the Cartesian plane can be define using the law of cosines and scalar product.

To understand better the sense of rotation lets develop cross product in terms of the functions homomorphism studied early.

$$\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = \|\vec{a}\| \|\vec{b}\| \sin(\alpha) \vec{n}$$

$$(\vec{a} \times \vec{b}) = \frac{(\vec{a} \times \vec{b})}{(\sqrt{Prod_{map}(Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(a_1, a_1), Prod_{map}(a_2, a_2)), Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(b_1, b_1), Prod_{map}(b_2, b_2)))})} \sin(\alpha) \vec{n}$$

and establishing the usual sense given on mechanics through the consideration of anticommutativity $\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = -\vec{b} \times \vec{a}$

$$\odot := \vec{a} \times \vec{b} ; \text{ (rotation anti clockwise)}$$

$$\otimes := \vec{b} \times \vec{a} ; \text{ (rotation clockwise)}$$

Finally lets note that if the coordinate

$$(*, **) = (ac - bd, ad + bc)$$

or

$$(**, *) = (ac - bd, ad + bc)$$

homomorphism properties maintains for $Prod_{map}$ function over Q function like was established early on this manuscript.

For this problem could appear that Q must have another identity when

$$Q'(a, b) = (-a, b)$$

However the numeration of quadrants given since this function is equivalent to that obtained for Q; with the difference that Q' when changes the sign of first coordinate besides apply a rotation of 180° over the Cartesian plane obtained. Due to this situation must be understood that

$$Q'(a, b) = -Q(a, b)$$

Same operation could be represented through the use of rotation matrix however this task will exceed the purpose of this manuscript; by this reason I am going to avoid for the moment the use of any matrix object.

2 Cayley tables for Monoid on Complex Numbers

Definition. Add_{map} and $Prod_{map}$ are epimorphism

Lets outline that Add_{map} and $Prod_{map}$ are not injective

Taking two vectors on C ; \vec{a} and \vec{b} such that in general

$$a \neq c \text{ and } b \neq d$$

if we multiply

$$a \cdot b \text{ and } c \cdot d$$

by definition of $Prod_{map}$

$$(a \cdot b) = Prod_{map}(a, b) \neq Prod_{map}(c, d) = (c \cdot d)$$

hence $Prod_{map}$ is not injective

by the other hand if we add

$$a + b \text{ and } c + d$$

by definition of Add_{map} we have

$$a + b = Add_{map}(a, b) \neq Add_{map}(c, d) = c + d$$

hence Add_{map} is not injective

Now lets note that both functions are surjectives:

$$Add_{map}(a, b) = a + b \in \mathfrak{R}$$

hence Add_{map} is surjective

$$Prod_{map}(a, b) = a \cdot b \in \mathfrak{R}$$

hence $Prod_{map}$ is surjective

An homomorphism that is surjective is called epimorphism.

Therefore

Add_{map} and $Prod_{map}$ are epimorphisms.

*) Exist a group (G, \cdot) such that $G = \{(a, b) \in C \mid a, b \in \mathfrak{R}; c = \frac{1}{a}; d = 0\}$

$$[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = [ac - bd, ad + bc] = (1, 0)$$

let be

$$c = \frac{1}{a}$$

and

$$b = d = 0$$

hence

$$[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = [a \cdot (\frac{1}{a}) - 0 \cdot 0, a \cdot 0 + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{a}] = (1, 0)$$

therefore the inverse \exists an inverse for each pair of the form $(a, 0)$ with expression $(\frac{1}{a}, 0)$

(\cdot)	$(1,0)$	$(-1,0)$	$(i,0)$	$(\frac{1}{a},0)$
$(1,0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C	e_C
$(-1,0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C	e_C
$(i,0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C	e_C
$(\frac{1}{a},0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C	e_C

*) Exist a group (H, \cdot) such that $H = \{(1, 0), (-1, 0), (\sqrt{-1}, 0)\}$

$$[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = [ac - bd, ad + bc] = (1, 0)$$

$$\text{if } c = \frac{1}{a}$$

and

$$b = d = 0$$

we can verified next equalities

$$(1, 0) \cdot (\frac{1}{1}, 0) = (1 \cdot \frac{1}{1} - 0 \cdot 0, 1 \cdot 0 + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{1}) = (1, 0)$$

$$(-1, 0) \cdot (\frac{1}{-1}, 0) = (-1 \cdot \frac{1}{-1} - 0 \cdot 0, -1 \cdot 0 + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{-1}) = (1, 0)$$

$$(\sqrt{-1}, 0) \cdot (\frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}}, 0) = (\sqrt{-1} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}} - 0 \cdot 0, \sqrt{-1} \cdot 0 + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}}) = (1, 0)$$

Must be established that the property to have inverse element is considered only for the pairs used early

$$[(1, 0), (-1, 0), (i, 0)]$$

to define the required group.

*) Cayley table of $H = \{(1, 0), (-1, 0), (\sqrt{-1}, 0)\}$

(\cdot)	$(1,0)$	$(-1,0)$	$(i,0)$
$(1,0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C
$(-1,0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C
$(i,0)$	e_C	e_C	e_C

*) H is a subgroup of G

lets take

$$h \in H \text{ hence } h \in G$$

like H form a group under \cdot (dot Argand product)

therefore

H is a subgroup of G

*) The generator set of Translation Group of G is $H' = \{(1, 0)\}$

Lets take the vector

$$\vec{e} = (1, 0) \text{ and define the set } H' = \{(1, 0)\}$$

$\vec{e} \in H'$ therefore $\vec{e} \in H$

like $H \subset G$

hence

$H' \subset G$

Now lets take equality by translation $=_T$

and lets note that

$$(1, 0) =_{\{T=h_1, h_2\}} (a, b); \text{ with } a, b \in \mathfrak{R} \text{ and } h_1, h_2 \in \mathfrak{R} \cup \{i\}$$

and

$$a = 1 + h_1 \text{ (or } -h_1 \text{ if its more convenient to plan Argand's product)}$$

$$b = 0 + h_2$$

Now lets announce the more convenient property of groups proposed by the author of this manuscript to define by translation equality ($=_T$) the "**Group of Translations**"

*) Associativity

$$(a, b) \cdot [(c, d) \cdot (e, f)] =_T [(a + h_1, b + h_2) \cdot (c + h_3, d + h_4)] \cdot (e + h_5, f + h_6)$$

with $h_1, \dots, h_6 \in \mathfrak{R}$ and possibly equal to zero

Even though it could be possible to give an equation to settle such problem; the difficulty to establish such equality resides on the possibility to give an adequate algebraic system where the relation between each pair of coordinates could be defined; i.e.

$$a = a + h_1$$

· · · · ·

etc

Must be almost intuitively that if the problem supplies all data; such equality can be given with proper values of each h_i to define the translation for each coordinate.

In other cases; I suppose that the solution must depend of how the variables relate between them taking into account the problem where such question is established.

Also is interesting to note that the subindex T will change of meaning when will establish

$$T = h_1, \dots, h_6$$

Indicating the value of each translation for each coordinate considered; instead to indicate the translation over each axis like was established early; ref. [3].

Considering the property of associativity we have:

$$(1, 0) \cdot [(1, 0) \cdot (1, 0)] = (1, 0) \cdot [(1)(1) - (0)(0), (1)(0) + (0)(1)]$$

$$(1, 0) \cdot (1, 0) = [(1)(1) - (0)(0), (1)(0) + (0)(1)] = (1, 0) \in H'$$

substituting the values of $a = c = e = 1$ and $b = d = f = 0$ on the term of right side we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
& [(a + h_1, b + h_2) \cdot (c + h_3, d + h_4)] \cdot (e + h_5, f + h_6) \\
&= [(1 + h_1)(1 + h_3) - (h_2)(h_4), (1 + h_1)(h_4) + (h_2)(1 + h_3)] \cdot (1 + h_5, h_6) \\
&= \{[(1 + h_1)(1 + h_3) - (h_2)(h_4)](1 + h_5) - [(1 + h_1)(h_4) + (h_2)(1 + h_3)]h_6, \\
&[(1 + h_1)(1 + h_3) - (h_2)(h_4)]h_6 + [(1 + h_1)(h_4) + (h_2)(1 + h_3)](1 + h_5)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Developing the first term of last coordinate we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
& [(1 + h_1)(1 + h_3) - (h_2)(h_4)](1 + h_5) \\
&= [(1)(1) + (1)(h_3) + (h_1)(h_3) - h_2h_4](1 + h_5) \\
&= [1 + h_3 + h_1h_3 - h_2h_4](1 + h_5) \\
&= (1)(1) + (1)(h_5) + (h_3)(1) + h_3h_5 + h_1h_3(1) + h_1h_3h_5 - h_2h_4(1) - h_2h_4h_5 \\
&= 1 + h_5 + h_3 + h_3h_5 + h_1h_3 + h_1h_3h_5 - h_2h_4 - h_2h_4h_5
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore translation terms are:

$$t_1 = h_5 + h_3 + h_3h_5 + h_1h_3 + h_1h_3h_5 - h_2h_4 - h_2h_4h_5 - [(1 + h_1)(h_4) + (h_2)(1 + h_3)]h_6$$

and

$$t_2 = [(1 + h_1)(1 + h_3) - (h_2)(h_4)]h_6 + [(1 + h_1)(h_4) + (h_2)(1 + h_3)](1 + h_5)$$

therefore

$$(1, 0) =_T [(1 + h_1, h_2) \cdot (1 + h_3, h_4)] \cdot (1 + h_5, h_6)$$

*) Identity element

$$(e_1, e_2) \cdot (a, b) = (a, b) =_T (a + h_1, b + h_2) = (e_1, e_2) \cdot (a + h_1, b + h_2)$$

Proof.

Lets obtain left equality

$$(1, 0) \cdot (a, b) = (1a - 0b, 1b + 0a) = (a, b)$$

and right equality

$$\begin{aligned}
(1, 0) \cdot (a + h_1, b + h_2) &= (1(a + h_1) - 0(b + h_2), 1(b + h_2) + 0(a + h_1)) \\
&= (a + h_1, b + h_2)
\end{aligned}$$

hence

$$(a, b) =_{\{T=h_1, h_2\}} (a + h_1, b + h_2)$$

*) **Inverse element**

$$(1, 0) = (a, b) \cdot (c, d) =_T (a + h_1, b + h_2) \cdot (c + h_3, d + h_4) = (1, 0)$$

Proof.

Lets take the conditions found to the inverse given early on this text:

with $c = \frac{1}{a}$ and $b = d = 0$ we have

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (1, 0)$$

like \mathbf{a} could have any value $\in \mathfrak{R} \cup \{i\}$

therefore

$$a' = a + h_1$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (a + h_1, b + h_2) \cdot (c + h_3, d + h_4) &= (a + h_1, h_2) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{a} + h_3, h_4\right) \\ &= (a', b') \cdot (c', d') = (a'c' - b'd', a'd' + b'c') \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{If } 1 + ah_3 + \frac{h_1}{a} + h_1h_3 - h_2h_4 = 1 + t_1$$

we will have next translation on each variable

$$t_1 = ah_3 + \frac{h_1}{a} + h_1h_3 - h_2h_4$$

$$t_2 = (a + h_1)(h_4) + h_2\left(\frac{1}{a} + h_3\right)$$

hence

$$(a + h_1, b + h_2) \cdot (c + h_3, d + h_4) =_T (1, 0)$$

and therefore

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) =_T (a + h_1, b + h_2) \cdot (c + h_3, d + h_4)$$

If the group of translations must contain all element sets that will fulfilled the binary relation; then must be understood that an auxiliary rule must be given to define the sites where such translation will have place. On the case argument here; the homomorphism $Prod_{map}$ supply additional conditions to establish this problem. Later will be shown the need to maintain both homomorphism function to define a "Projective Space" since the images sets of each functions and will be shown also its relationship with the field of real numbers.

Therefore the group $H' = \{(1, 0)\}$ defines the group of translation (T, \cdot)

$$\text{where } T = \{(a, b) \mid \forall a, b \in \mathfrak{R} \cup \{i\}; (a, b) =_T (1, 0)\}$$

with the definition given here for such purpose

*) Exist a projective space of $Prod_{map}(a, b)$; $Add_{map}(a, b)$ equal to real space.

$$\mathfrak{R} \cup \{i\} = E$$

$$\phi : E \times E \rightarrow R$$

$$(a, b) \mapsto \phi(a, b)$$

If $\phi = Prod_{map}$ hence

$$\phi\{(a, b) \cdot (c, d)\} = Prod_{map}\{(a, b) \cdot (c, d)\} = a^2cd + abc^2 - abd^2 - b^2cd = p \in \mathfrak{R}$$

If $\phi = Add_{map}$ hence

$$\phi\{(a, b) \cdot (c, d)\} = Add_{map}\{(a, b) \cdot (c, d)\} = ac - bd + ad + bc = q \in \mathfrak{R}$$

Now consider next properties $\forall a, b, c, d \in E$; to establish the existence of the real numbers field; we are going to propose first certain conditions to reach this goal; if well is it possible to define another conditions; the general problem of factorizing any \mathbf{p} or \mathbf{q} like is considered since $Prod_{map}$ and Add_{map} must be established first before to take this definition like main condition.

$$*) \forall q \in \mathfrak{R}; \exists -\frac{1}{q} \in \mathfrak{R}$$

Some conditions found for this problem are:

$$a = \frac{1}{q}; b = 0; c = 1; d = 0$$

$$a = 1; b = 0; c = 0; d = \frac{1}{\delta}$$

$$a = 1; b = 0; c = \frac{1}{\gamma}; d = 0$$

$$a = 0; b = \frac{1}{\beta}; c = 0; d = -1$$

Hence an enough condition to prove the existence of $\frac{1}{q}$ for every $q \in \mathfrak{R}$ when

$$\frac{1}{q} = Add_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] \text{ is}$$

$$a = \frac{1}{q}; b = 0; c = 1; d = 0$$

$$*) \exists -q \in \mathfrak{R}; \forall q \in \mathfrak{R}$$

An enough condition to prove the existence of $-q$ when

$$-q = Add_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] \text{ is}$$

$$b = 0; d = 1; c = 1; a < 0$$

Similar conditions can be given since $Prod_{map}$ function to establish early properties like

$$Prod_{map}[(a, b) \cdot (c, d)] = a^2cd + abc^2 - abd^2 - b^2cd = p$$

with $b = 0; a = 1; d = 1$ and c define conveniently to be used like $c \in E$ and fulfilled early and next properties.

$$*) \text{ Exists the additive identity } (\exists e_{Rsum} = 0)$$

On ref[2.3] its shown next property:

$$Prod_{map}(e_C) = e_{\mathfrak{R}}$$

$$Prod_{map}(1, 0) = (1 \cdot 0) = 0 = e_{\mathfrak{Rsum}}$$

$$*) \text{ Exists the multiplicative identity } (\exists e_{Rprod} = 1)$$

$$Add_{map}(e_C) = e_{\mathfrak{R}}$$

$$Add_{map}(1, 0) = (1 + 0) = 1 = e_{\mathfrak{Rprod}}$$

$$*) \text{ Closure } (x \in \mathfrak{R})$$

Taking both results established by both homomorphism we have that this property is fulfilled for **Addition** and **Multiplication** on real numbers because they are real numbers; i.e. $\forall p \forall q \in \mathfrak{R}$ define since $Prod_{map}$ and Add_{map} to be on \mathfrak{R} is satisfied.

Note that like before

a is link with q

or

c is link with p

hence

$c \in E$

under this definition

$i = \sqrt{-1} \in \mathfrak{R}$

and by heritage the properties of

$-a =_A a := -a < a$

maintains

On this way

$-1 =_A 1$ and $\sqrt{-1} =_A \sqrt{1}$

could establish that $i = 1$

*) Commutativity ($x \cdot y = y \cdot x$)

To be real numbers \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{a} fulfilled commutativity of **Addition** and **Multiplication**.

*) Associativity ($x \cdot (y \cdot z) = (x \cdot y) \cdot z$)

To be real numbers \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{a} fulfilled associativity of **Addition** and **Multiplication**.

*) Distributive ($x \cdot (y + z) = x \cdot y + x \cdot z$)

To be real numbers \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{a} fulfilled distributive property.

*) Trichotomy

To be real numbers \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{a} fulfilled

$a < c$;

$a = c$

or

$a > c$

*) Trichotomy of sumation and product

If we have

a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n

and

c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n

Hence

$$\prod_{k=1}^n a_k (\sum_{j=1}^m c_j) < \prod_{k'=1}^{n'} a_{k'} (\sum_{j'=1}^{m'} c_{j'})$$

with $n \neq n'$; $k \neq k'$; $j \neq j'$; and $m \neq m'$

About Algebraic Structure of equality $=_A$

I suppose that the full collection of values of a,b, c, d that could be used to define the solutions of Argand's product and be used through homomorphism Add_{map} and $Prod_{map}$; to project the real space must be considered to establish an special structure of homomorphism; maybe an structure kind group.

In some point this definition must be guide to establish the full algebraic structure derived from abstract equality; being a good candidate until this moment; the use of definitions about Universal Algebra.

However the kind of mathematical object needed to establish a "pattern" for a,b,c and d is not very clear for me in this moment, due to the big size of the polynomials obtained. I hope into the future the establishment of some "tensor algebra" linked with the notion of *quirality* used on this work could be of help to understand better this algebraic problem. By the other hand I do not discard that the solution could comes from some theoretical framework defined to study some mechanical problem; for example about atomic subparticles.

Final Notes.

It is important to outline the difference between arithmetic meaning given by the equality = and the meaning given here for "geometrical equality" through the use of $=_A$.

The arithmetic meaning can not be avoided; when we try to establish that $-1 = 1$ we are defining a fallacy; because we know that the sense of use of equality sign works in this way.

However the sense of "equal distance" used to give conditions of homomorphism; when it is preserve on the analysis of such mathematical objects over the Cartesian plane must guide to the establishment of equality in abstract sense; before to transform and vanish this notion of "geometrical equality" through the use of "absolute value" and "euclidean distance" to adjust the arithmetic sense of quantities obtained since the Cartesian plane.

3 References

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